

1 **Calculating Chlorine Concentration Bounds in Water**
2 **Distribution Networks: A Backtracking**
3 **Uncertainty-Bounding Approach**

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7 **Key Points:**

- 8 • A novel methodology for calculating chlorine concentration bounds in water dis-
9 tribution networks is proposed and tested.
- 10 • Bounds are calculated analytically, without the need for Monte-Carlo simulations,
11 considering both water flow and parameter uncertainties.
- 12 • A real-time parameter estimation algorithm is combined with the proposed method-
13 ology to improve the calculated bounds and applied on a case study with real data.

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Abstract

The estimation of chlorine concentration in water distribution networks is a challenging task due to hydraulic and water-quality parameter uncertainties. In this work we propose a methodology for calculating chlorine concentration bounds at node locations of water distribution networks which is suitable for sensor fault and contamination detection purposes. The proposed *Backtracking Uncertainty Bounding Algorithm* (BUBA) considers known bounds on hydraulic states and water-quality model parameters to calculate the chlorine concentration bounds. The validity of the calculated bounds is demonstrated using a large number of Monte-Carlo simulations on benchmark networks. Moreover, the proposed methodology can be used in conjunction with a real-time parameter estimation algorithm, as it allows the use of time-varying bulk reaction coefficients. A parameter estimation algorithm is designed and implemented to approximate the unknown bulk reaction coefficient of water at the sources of the WDN, which are typically water tanks filled with water originating from different sources. The BUBA then uses these time-varying parameters to improve the chlorine concentration bounds, as demonstrated in a case study with real data from a water transport network.

1 Introduction

The most recent EU directive on the quality of water intended for human consumption (European Commission, 2018) emphasizes the importance of water quality monitoring for reducing the risks to health from drinking water, with chlorine by-products being among the quality parameters recommended for monitoring. Chlorine is commonly used by water utilities as a disinfectant in Water Distribution Networks (WDN). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), a chlorine residual needs to be sustained throughout the drinking water network which should be sufficient to deactivate water-borne pathogens and, at the same time, small enough to reduce the formation of harmful chlorine by-products (Mouly et al., 2010). Additionally, due to the fact that certain contaminants will affect chlorine residuals in a specific way (e.g., a bacterial toxin may decrease the concentration of free chlorine due to its reaction dynamics) (Helbling & VanBriesen, 2009), chlorine residuals can be used as key indicators of contamination events (Hall et al., 2007).

The installation of on-line chlorine sensors can enhance monitoring capabilities of chlorine residuals and enable more timely control actions. For contamination event detection, water-quality sensors may be installed which can monitor multiple parameters (for example, pH, free chlorine, total organic carbon) and detect changes in water quality. The placement of such sensors in WDN in order to detect a contamination event has been a subject of research for years (Hart & Murray, 2010; Eliades & Polycarpou, 2010). The problem is posed as a multi-objective optimization, with one of the objectives being the minimization of the number of sensors due to their high capital and maintenance costs (Zeng et al., 2016), while addressing the uncertainty present in these real world systems is also a crucial component of these methodologies (Sankary & Ostfeld, 2018). Single-parameter sensors (such as free chlorine concentration sensors) are cheaper than multi-parameter sensors, and using them not only for chlorine residual monitoring but also for contamination event detection, could significantly reduce the health risks from contaminated drinking water. However, in order to determine whether a sensor reading is abnormal (e.g., due to a contamination), it needs to be compared with an estimate of the expected concentration at the sensor location. The estimated concentration can be calculated using water-quality models (Rossman & Boulos, 1996). These are mathematical representations of the physical and chemical laws that describe chemical transport and reaction in WDN and are used to calculate the water-quality states, which, in this work, are the chlorine concentration at nodes of the WDN.

Figure 1. Dependence of water quality dynamics on hydraulic dynamics in a water distribution network.

64 Chlorine concentration at a network location depends on the chlorine input, but
 65 also on consumer water demands and hydraulic actions which affect pipe water flows,
 66 as seen in Fig. 1. Due to the time-varying nature of the typically unknown consumer de-
 67 mands, water-quality also exhibits a time-varying behavior. Some approaches have ex-
 68 ploited the apparent periodicity of water demands, and by extent, water flows, to cre-
 69 ate time-varying water-quality models using online learning (Polycarpou et al., 2002).
 70 These approaches omit the information provided by hydraulic sensors, which may lead
 71 to significant estimation errors. In fact, the variability of water flows is the greatest source
 72 of uncertainty in water-quality models (Pasha & Lansey, 2010). The most common ap-
 73 proach to deal with modeling uncertainty due to water flows is using them as an input
 74 to the water-quality model, by assuming that the hydraulics are constant (steady-state)
 75 and known over a period of time called the hydraulic step (Rossman, 2000). However,
 76 hydraulic state estimates obtained when solving the flow network during this period may
 77 be inaccurate due to errors in modeling of water demands and other model uncertain-
 78 ties, such as unknown pipe roughness coefficients (Hutton et al., 2014). Recent efforts
 79 in developing hydraulic-state estimation methodologies combine measurements from hy-
 80 draulic sensors to obtain estimates of flows and pressures (Tshehla et al., 2017). These
 81 methodologies try to overcome the challenge of using a small number of measurements
 82 compared to the system states to obtain reliable hydraulic-state estimates, while also cal-
 83 ibrating model parameters and water demands (Kumar et al., 2010; Díaz et al., 2017).
 84 More advanced methodologies have also been developed which are able to quantify the
 85 hydraulic-state estimation error (Díaz et al., 2016b). In many cases, providing a range
 86 of values for each state is more useful to an operator than providing estimates with no
 87 indication of their accuracy. The authors proposed such an approach in (Vrachimis et
 88 al., 2019), in which uncertainties affecting the hydraulics are modeled as intervals using
 89 their lower and upper bounds, thus requiring less *a priori* information than probabilis-
 90 tic modeling approaches. The so-called Iterative Hydraulic Interval State-Estimator (IHISE)
 91 then uses sensor measurements to calculate bounds on water flows (Vrachimis et al., 2019).
 92

93 Chlorine reaction dynamics in WDN, in most of the cases, are not known; as a re-
 94 sult, empirical models (i.e., models created from laboratory and field experiments) are
 95 typically considered (Hua et al., 1999; Clark et al., 1994). A common assumption in the
 96 water research literature is that chlorine dynamics are first-order linear, with some stud-
 97 ies contacted in real networks showing this to be a good approximation (Monteiro et al.,
 98 2017). Other studies are in favor of using more complex dynamics such as a second or-
 99 der model (Clark, 1998), as well as the use of differential-algebraic equations to model
 100 fast reactions (Shang et al., 2008). In the first-order model, chlorine reaction dynamics
 101 depend on the bulk-water reaction coefficient (water source), the wall reaction coefficient
 102 (pipe material) and the mass transfer coefficient (chlorine transfer from bulk water to
 103 pipe walls) (Rossman et al., 1994). An estimate of wall and mass transfer coefficients can

104 be made available given pipe material and age (Vasconcelos et al., 1997). The bulk re-
105 action rate dominates the decay dynamics, except in the case of highly reactive metal-
106 lic pipes (Monteiro et al., 2017). Bulk reaction rates are usually unknown and may vary
107 due to the use of water originating from different sources (e.g. combining treated wa-
108 ter from dams and desalination plants in different ratios) or fluctuations in temperature
109 (Monteiro et al., 2017).

110 The water-quality modeling results in a set of hyperbolic partial differential equa-
111 tions (PDEs). In general, Eulerian or Lagrangian numerical methods can be used to find
112 an approximate solution to the PDEs (Rossman & Boulos, 1996). The Eulerian meth-
113 ods divide each link of the network into a number of equally sized segments, and react
114 and transport water between segments at fixed intervals of time. The Lagrangian meth-
115 ods track the position of variable-sized segments of water in each link, computing new
116 conditions at either fixed time intervals or at times when a new segment reaches the down-
117 stream node of a link. The latter was adopted and used by the EPANET software, which
118 uses a distributed model of water-quality, efficient at calculating output information at
119 all network locations over time (Rossman, 2000). Another approach, belonging to the
120 Lagrangian family, is the so-called Particle-Backtracking Algorithm (PBA) (Shang et al.,
121 2002) which tracks individual water parcels from specific nodes (output) to chlorine in-
122 jection nodes (input) backwards in time. This method has the advantage of retaining
123 input-output relationship information, such as the time delay of injected chlorine reach-
124 ing a sensor node. The PBA method has been proven useful in calibrating pipe wall re-
125 action coefficients, due to its ability to calculate the flow paths between input and out-
126 put and creating an input-output model (Zierolf et al., 1998).

127 A model intended for water-quality monitoring as well as contamination detection
128 should be able to quantify the estimation errors which arise from the combined hydraulic
129 and water-quality parameter uncertainty. The generation of tight adaptive thresholds
130 on the water-quality states can then be used for sensor fault diagnosis and contamina-
131 tion detection (Isermann, 2006). One approach to do this is proposed in (Eliades et al.,
132 2015), where chlorine concentration bounds are calculated through Monte-Carlo Sim-
133 ulations (MCS) using the Lagrangian model of EPANET software and used as detection
134 thresholds. The uncertain water demands and chlorine reaction rates are varied randomly
135 within pre-defined bounds in each simulation. This is basically a simulation-oriented ap-
136 proach to set-membership state-estimation, in which uncertainty is modeled as an ad-
137 ditive bounded error of which only the bounds are known. The result is a set-bounded
138 state estimate, e.g. a state defined by an interval instead of a single value (Raïssi et al.,
139 2012).

140 Powerful methodologies in set-bounded state estimation have been developed in
141 the literature which can be applied on nonlinear discrete-time systems with unknown-
142 but-bounded uncertainties (Rego et al., 2020). However, the distributed nature of water-
143 quality models in time and space make it challenging for generic set-membership esti-
144 mation methodologies to be applied in practice. A notable set-membership application
145 to water-quality is made in (Łangowski & Brdys, 2007, 2017), where a distributed interval-
146 model of water-quality is formulated following the Lagrangian modeling approach, based
147 on known-bounded uncertainties on water flows and water-quality parameters. The re-
148 searchers go a step further by proposing an interval observer structure for chlorine resid-
149 ual estimation. However, a drawback of this modeling approach is the increased interval-
150 model complexity that occurs as the network size increases. Moreover, the switching na-
151 ture of the model due to water flow reversal does not allow for sufficient stability con-
152 ditions for the observer design, thus the assumption is made that flows are positive. An-
153 other key assumption is that the bulk reaction rate bounds are known *a priori*. In prac-
154 tice, these bounds may be unknown and time-varying if water originates from different
155 sources. The proposed approach cannot facilitate real-time bulk reaction rate estima-
156 tion as it does not consider time-varying parameters. As a result the uncertainty can-

157 not be reduced, and the generated bounds are conservative, which increases the possi-
 158 bility of false negatives.

159 In this work we propose a methodology to calculate chlorine concentration bounds
 160 at nodes of WDN, using an input-output modeling approach, suitable to be used for sen-
 161 sor fault and contamination detection purposes. The proposed approach uses hydraulic-
 162 state estimates as an input and calculates chlorine concentration bounds at the defined
 163 output locations (e.g., sensor locations). Due to the fact that this methodology is able
 164 to identify the specific flow paths that affect the concentration at the output and exclude
 165 from the calculations parts of the network that do not affect the output, computational
 166 complexity is reduced, especially in large networks. Additionally, path information is re-
 167 tained and can be used for parameter estimation to reduce uncertainty. An additional
 168 benefit is that bulk reaction rate of individual water parcels can be tracked, thus allow-
 169 ing for time-variable bulk reaction rates in the network, which is useful when the sys-
 170 tem is supplied by multiple sources. The proposed Backtracking Uncertainty Bounding
 171 Algorithm (BUBA) was first introduced in a conference paper (Vrachimis et al., 2015)
 172 and it is extended here to be able to use interval flow estimates, while taking into con-
 173 sideration bounded time-varying uncertainties on chlorine decay rates. Extensive Monte-
 174 Carlo simulations of chlorine concentration using EPANET are carried out to demon-
 175 strate the ability of the methodology to provide tight bounding estimates. The proposed
 176 approach does not use sensor measurements to calculate chlorine concentration, however,
 177 we demonstrate the ability of the methodology to facilitate parameter estimation algo-
 178 rithms which use the available measurements. A real-time parameter estimation algo-
 179 rithm is designed to approximate the bulk reaction coefficient of water at the sources of
 180 the WDN, which are typically water tanks filled with water originating from different
 181 sources. The BUBA then uses the time-varying bulk reaction coefficient to improve the
 182 bounded chlorine concentration estimates throughout the network, as demonstrated in
 183 a case study with real data from a water transport network.

184 This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 formulates the problem of modeling
 185 chlorine concentration in a network with uncertain flows and water quality parameters.
 186 Section 3 then describes the proposed Backtracking Uncertainty Bounding Algorithm.
 187 In Section 4 a parameter estimation algorithm is described which estimates the chlorine
 188 bulk reaction coefficient at the sources of the WDN, which are typically water tanks. These
 189 estimates are then used in the proposed BUBA to calculate chlorine concentration through-
 190 out the network. Illustrative results of applying the proposed BUBA on two benchmark
 191 networks are presented in Section 5.1 and 5.2. In Section 5.3, results on a real network
 192 case study are shown, in which the BUBA is used in conjunction with the designed real-
 193 time parameter estimation algorithm. The models, code and data generated during this
 194 study are available in a code repository for reproducibility. The link to the repository
 195 is provided in the Acknowledgments Section.

196 2 Problem formulation

197 This work considers water distribution networks containing water tanks and other
 198 hydraulic elements such as pumps and valves. The topology of a WDN is modeled by
 199 a directed graph denoted as $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{L})$. Let $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, n_n\}$ be the set of all nodes,
 200 where $|\mathcal{N}| = n_n$ is the total number of nodes. These represent junctions of pipes, con-
 201 sumer water demand locations, reservoirs and tanks. Let $\mathcal{L} = \{l_{ij} : i, j \in \mathcal{N}\}$ be the set
 202 of links such that link l_{ij} connects node i with node j , and $|\mathcal{L}| = n_l$ is the total num-
 203 ber of links. The notation for links defines the initial convention of flow direction in the
 204 specific link, i.e., link l_{ij} has a positive flow when water flows from node i to node j and
 205 negative flow when water flows from node j to node i . These represent network pipes,
 206 water pumps and pipe valves, with the last two being the main hydraulic control elements
 207 in a water network. In addition, let $\mathcal{M}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathcal{G})$ be the general model of a water distribu-
 208 tion network which associates network parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ with the network structure repre-

209 sented by the graph \mathcal{G} . Network parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are typically assumed time-invariant, ex-
 210 cept in the case of bulk reaction rates which may vary significantly.

211 2.1 Hydraulics modeling

212 The hydraulic-state associated with nodes is the *hydraulic head*, indicated by h_i ,
 213 and is a specific measure of water pressure or water level above a geodetic datum. Each
 214 node $i \in \mathcal{N}$ is also associated with a water consumer demand at the node location, de-
 215 noted by d_i . The unknown quantity associated with a link l_{ij} which connects node i to
 216 node j is the *water flow*, indicated by q_{ij} . Hydraulic network parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_h$ represent
 217 parameters needed for hydraulic state estimation such as pipe lengths, diameters and
 218 roughness coefficients, with $\boldsymbol{\theta}_h$ being a subvector of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

219 Hydraulic-state estimation is enabled using hydraulic-sensors in an observable con-
 220 figuration (Díaz et al., 2016a) which send measurements at a discrete time-step k . A suit-
 221 able hydraulic-state estimation algorithm then uses these measurements and the network
 222 model $\mathcal{M}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_h, \mathcal{G})$ to estimate the complete hydraulic-state given by $\boldsymbol{x}_h(k) = [\boldsymbol{h}^\top(k), \boldsymbol{q}^\top(k)]^\top$,
 223 where $\boldsymbol{h} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_n}$ is the vector of heads at each node, and $\boldsymbol{q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l}$ is the vector of flows
 224 at each link.

225 When estimating hydraulic-states there are significant uncertainties in measure-
 226 ments, as well as model parameters. Measuring devices give readings which include mea-
 227 surement noise, causing the resulting reading to deviate from actual measured states.
 228 Let $\boldsymbol{y}_h(k) = C_h \boldsymbol{x}_h(k) + \boldsymbol{\nu}(k)$, where \boldsymbol{y}_h is the hydraulic measurements vector, C_h is
 229 the output matrix and $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ is the measurement noise vector. Most importantly, estimated
 230 values of water demands (called pseudo-measurements) which may be needed for observ-
 231 ability, are associated with significant uncertainty and lack statistical characterization
 232 of the error to the actual demands (Andersen et al., 2001). Parameter uncertainties in-
 233 clude mainly pipe roughness coefficients, and the less uncertain pipe lengths and diam-
 234 eters.

235 In this work, it is assumed that uncertainties are characterized by a uniform prob-
 236 ability distribution function and thus uncertain parameters are modeled as intervals. The
 237 motivation for using this assumption is because several studies have proposed that the
 238 uncertainties in WDN are better represented by confidence bounds instead of other stati-
 239 statistical characterizations such as the normal distribution (Bargiela et al., 2003; Blesa et
 240 al., 2010; Cuguelero-Escofet et al., 2015). For notational convenience, we adopt the con-
 241 vention of denoting intervals with a tilde. Let $\tilde{\boldsymbol{v}} = [\underline{\boldsymbol{v}}, \overline{\boldsymbol{v}}]$ be a closed interval vector, where
 242 $\underline{\boldsymbol{v}}$ is the lower bound vector and $\overline{\boldsymbol{v}}$ is the upper bound vector, such that: $\tilde{\boldsymbol{v}} = \{\boldsymbol{v} \in \mathbb{R}^n :$
 243 $\underline{v}_i \leq v_i \leq \overline{v}_i, \forall i = \{1, \dots, n\}\}$, and n is the size of the vector. We assume that bounds
 244 on model parameters and measurement noise exist and are available at each time-step
 245 k . Bounds on hydraulic-states can then be calculated using the interval hydraulic-state
 246 estimator (IHISE) described in (Vrachimis et al., 2019). The interval-hydraulic-states
 247 are indicated by $\tilde{\boldsymbol{x}}_h(k) = [\tilde{\boldsymbol{h}}^\top(k), \tilde{\boldsymbol{q}}^\top(k)]^\top$.

248 2.2 Water quality modeling

249 Water-quality-state in this work refers to the concentration of chlorine in the wa-
 250 ter at the nodes of the network. Chlorine concentration at a node i is indicated by $c_i(k)$,
 251 with k corresponding to the water-quality model discrete time step. Here, for simplic-
 252 ity, it is assumed that the quality model step duration Δt_q is equal to the hydraulic step
 253 duration Δt_h , i.e., $\Delta t_q = \Delta t_h = \Delta t$. The quality time-step affects the size of each wa-
 254 ter parcel being tracked, so Δt is set sufficiently small such that any errors arising from
 255 space discretization are negligible. It is noted here that, computationally, the accuracy
 256 of the proposed methodology depends only on the water-quality time-step and the only

257 requirement regarding the hydraulic time-step is to be equal or larger than the water-
 258 quality step.

259 Chlorine concentration is regulated in tanks using chlorine injection pumps, where
 260 the mass of chlorine injected in tank of node i is known and indicated by $u_i(k)$. More-
 261 over, we assume that tanks have one distinct inlet and one outlet which are both moni-
 262 tored by chlorine sensors. Finally, tanks and locations in the network which have chlo-
 263 rine booster stations (Kang & Lansey, 2010) are considered nodes with known concen-
 264 tration belonging to set $\mathcal{U} \subset \mathcal{N}$. Known concentration at booster stations is assumed
 265 to be achieved through the use of a local feedback controller, which uses readings from
 266 a local chlorine sensor and a chlorine dosing pump to regulate the concentration at the
 267 booster station location (Polycarpou et al., 2002).

268 The dynamics describing the change of chlorine concentration in the network are
 269 governed by: (1) the physical laws of chlorine transport, which depend on the water flows
 270 $\mathbf{q}(k)$ and the structure of the network \mathcal{G} , (2) the chemical laws of chlorine reactions, which
 271 depend on the decay rate of chlorine. Chlorine decay in turn depends on two factors: (2a)
 272 the organic substances present in the water which result in the so-called *bulk reaction*
 273 *rate*, indicated by the time-dependent $r^b(k) < 0 \ \forall k$ and (2b) the pipe l_{ij} the water
 274 flows in, which is characterized by the *pipe wall reaction rate*, indicated by $r_{ij}^w < 0$ (Rossman
 275 et al., 1994). Bulk and pipe wall reaction rates are water-quality-model parameters of
 276 interest, indicated by $\boldsymbol{\theta}_r(k)$, and in this work it is assumed that only bounds on their true
 277 values are known.

278 The true chlorine decay dynamics in pipe networks are unknown, so modeling as-
 279 sumptions which approximate these dynamics are used (Rossman et al., 1994). Specif-
 280 ically, it is assumed that the chlorine decay in pipe networks can be described by a lin-
 281 ear first order reaction model with varying reaction rate. Chlorine concentration at a node
 282 j is found by decaying the chlorine which originated from node i as follows:

$$283 \quad c_j(t) = c_i(t - t_d) e^{r(t) \cdot t_d} + \eta(r), \quad (1)$$

284 where t_d is the time chlorine has spend in the pipe or detention time, $r(t) = r_{ij}^w + r^b(t)$
 285 is the total decay rate in pipe l_{ij} , and $\eta(r)$ is an unknown function of the decay rate cor-
 286 responding to modeling uncertainty. Notice that bulk decay rate $r^b(t)$ is assumed to be
 287 time-varying. Also note that for the purpose of calculating chlorine concentration, spe-
 288 cial links such as pumps and valves are represented as pipes of appropriate length, di-
 289 ameter and wall reaction rate. Moreover, it is assumed that there is instant and com-
 290 plete mixing of chlorine in pipe junctions. The concentration at a pipe junction j , in the
 291 case when $j \notin \mathcal{U}$ and thus the concentration is not known, can be calculated as follows:

$$292 \quad c_j(k) = \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}_j(k)} q_{ij}(k) c_{ij}(k)}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}_j(k)} q_{ij}(k)}, \quad (2)$$

293 where $c_{ij}(k)$ is defined as the chlorine contribution from a pipe l_{ij} to node j at time-step
 294 k , and $\mathcal{P}_j(k)$ is the set of all pipes that bring water into node j at time k .

295 The chlorine concentration inside the network can be calculated using a water-quality
 296 estimator, which is a function that uses the physical and chemical laws that describe chlo-
 297 rine transport and reaction in water networks, to calculate the quality states. Let the
 298 nonlinear function $f_c(\cdot)$ be a water quality estimator to be defined, that calculates the
 299 chlorine concentration at the nodes of a network. The inputs and outputs of this func-
 300 tion can be written as follows:

$$301 \quad \mathbf{c}(k) = f_c(\mathbf{c}(0), \mathbf{U}_c(k_m), \mathbf{Q}(k_m); \mathcal{M}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_r(k); \mathcal{G})), \quad (3)$$

302 where:

- 303 • $\mathbf{c}(0)$ is the initial chlorine concentration at the nodes of the network,
- 304 • $\mathbf{U}_c(k_m) = [\mathbf{u}_c(k), \mathbf{u}_c(k-1), \dots, \mathbf{u}_c(k-m)]$ is a sequence of chlorine injection
- 305 control vectors,
- 306 • $\mathbf{Q}(k_m) = [\mathbf{q}(k), \mathbf{q}(k-1), \dots, \mathbf{q}(k-m)]$ is a sequence of flow vectors,
- 307 • $m \in \mathbb{N}^+$ is the memory of function $f_c(\cdot)$, denoting the number of previous time-
- 308 steps from which information is needed to evaluate this function.

309 Here we note that the aforementioned modeling of chlorine reactions and kinetics in WDN
 310 is a simplified model which approximates the actual chemistry and physics of chlorine
 311 in these networks and has been shown to work reasonably well (Monteiro et al., 2020).
 312 Some aspects of modeling water-quality in WDN however are more complex, such as the
 313 effect of water stagnation on chlorine residuals at dead-end sections where water demand
 314 can be zero (Abokifa et al., 2016, 2020).

315 2.3 Incorporating uncertainty in water-quality models

316 When estimating water quality, there is significant uncertainty due to uncertain
 317 water flows, uncertain wall reaction rates and unknown and time-varying bulk reaction
 318 rates (due to the use of water from different sources). In this work, the uncertain wa-
 319 ter flows and reaction rates are modeled as intervals by assuming known lower and up-
 320 per bounds on their given values. A chlorine concentration bounding estimator $\tilde{f}_c(\cdot)$ can
 321 then be designed which is able to calculate bounds on chlorine concentration for a node
 322 i in the network, expressed as follows:

$$323 \quad \tilde{c}_i(k) = \tilde{f}_c \left(\mathbf{c}(0), \mathbf{U}_c(k_m), \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(k_m); \mathcal{M}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_r(k_m); \mathcal{G}) \right), \quad (4)$$

324 where:

- 325 • $\tilde{c}_i(k) = [\underline{c}_i(k), \bar{c}_i(k)]$,
- 326 • $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(k_m)$ is a sequence of interval flow vectors, such that $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}(k) = [\underline{\mathbf{q}}(k), \bar{\mathbf{q}}(k)]$,
- 327 • $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_r(k_m)$ is a sequence of interval parameter vectors, such that $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_r(k) = [\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_r(k), \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_r(k)]$.

328 The aim of this work is to design a methodology which realises the function $\tilde{f}_c(\cdot)$ in (4).

329 3 The Backtracking Uncertainty Bounding Algorithm

330 On-line chlorine concentration sensors can enhance the monitoring capabilities of
 331 chlorine residuals in WDN, however, in order to determine whether a sensor reading is
 332 abnormal (e.g., due to a contamination), it needs to be compared with an estimate of
 333 the expected concentration at the sensor location. Such an estimator should be able to
 334 quantify the estimation uncertainty arising from uncertain water flows and time-varying
 335 reaction rates. A chlorine concentration bounding estimator $\tilde{f}_c(\cdot)$ is realised in this sec-
 336 tion by introducing the *Backtracking Uncertainty Bounding Algorithm* (BUBA). This
 337 methodology uses interval hydraulic-state estimates, specifically water flows $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}(k)$, from
 338 the IHISE algorithm described in (Vrachimis et al., 2019) as input. It can also use time-
 339 varying water-quality parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_r(k)$, specifically bulk reaction rate estimate $\hat{r}(k)$ which
 340 is updated online using a suitable parameter estimation algorithm. An example of such
 341 a parameter estimation algorithm is presented in Section 4, which estimates the bulk re-
 342 action rate $\hat{r}_{out}(k)$ at the output of water supply tanks. Chlorine sensor measurements
 343 $\mathbf{y}_c(k)$ can then be compared with the chlorine concentration bounding estimates $\tilde{c}(k)$
 344 calculated by the BUBA to detect contamination events using a suitable contamination
 345 detection logic. A general diagram illustrating the overall process is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Information flow diagram of the proposed methodology.

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3.1 The backtracking approach

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According to the backtracking approach (Zierolf et al., 1998; Shang et al., 2002), chlorine concentration of *water parcels* arriving at sensor locations are back-tracked throughout the network until boundary conditions are reached. These boundary conditions are: (a) Space boundary, which is the case when the parcel reaches an input node in \mathcal{U} of which the concentration is known; (b) Time boundary, which is the case when the water parcel reaches the initial time-step $k = 0$ at which the chlorine concentration $c(0)$ of all nodes is known. A key advantage of the backtracking approach is that only the concentration at nodes is being tracked, thus leading to a model with a reduced number of states. A consequence of this approach is that the initial concentration of links is not required. Note that if the simulation is executed for a sufficient time, any chlorine initially present in the network will have decayed. Thereafter, the output concentration will only depend on chlorine originating from input nodes and the initial concentration will not affect the results.

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3.2 The BUBA functions

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The BUBA consists of four functions that recursively call each other to collectively compute the chlorine concentration at a node. An illustration of the recursive calls and information flow of the BUBA functions is shown in Fig. 3. The first function called is *BoundCheck* which checks the boundary conditions for a given node j and time-step k . If boundary conditions have not been reached, *PipesJunction* is called to calculate the concentration and bulk reaction rate at node j considering this is a pipe junction. To do this, *PipesJunction* calls *PipeContribution* which provides the chlorine contribution and bulk reaction rates of each pipe connected to the junction. In turn, *PipeContribution*

Figure 3. Information flow between the BUBA functions

369 *tion* calls *Upstream&Time* to provide the upstream node and detention times for each
 370 pipe, while it also recursively calls *BoundCheck* to provide the chlorine concentration at
 371 the upstream node at a previous time-step. A description of each function follows.

372 **3.3 Function 1: *Upstream&Time* — Detention time in single pipe with** 373 **uncertainty**

374 Here the methodology for finding the detention time and upstream node of a water
 375 parcel moving in a single pipe under uncertain water flow is described.

376 Consider the simple case of a single pipe, as in Fig. 4, of which the output node
 377 j receives water from the input node i . Chlorine transport is expressed by finding the
 378 time the water parcel has spent in the pipe, or detention time, indicated by $t_d \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$.
 379 The detention time is calculated by finding the number of elapsed time-steps $k_d \in \mathbb{N}^+$,
 380 or delay, since the water parcel currently arriving at node j has entered pipe l_{ij} . Note
 381 that the upstream node $p \in \mathcal{N}$, defined as the node from which the parcel originated
 382 from, should be determined since this node can be either i or j due to flow reversal. The
 383 auxiliary quantity x_d defines the position of the water parcel in the pipe, using the wa-
 384 ter flow q_{ij} and the pipe cross section area α_{ij} as follows:

$$385 \quad x_d = \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_{ij}} \sum_{m=1}^{k_d} q_{ij}(k-m). \quad (5)$$

Figure 4. Water parcel arriving at node j through pipe l_{ij}

386 The delay k_d and the upstream node p is calculated by finding the minimum value of k_d
 387 that results in: (i) x_d being larger than the length of the pipe λ_{ij} , in which case the re-
 388 sulting upstream node $p = i$, or (ii) x_d being less than zero, in which case the upstream
 389 node $p = j$:

$$390 \quad k_d^* = \{ \min (k_d \in \mathbb{N}^+) : x_d \notin [0, \lambda_{ij}] \} \quad (6)$$

391 The exact detention time t_d is then calculated as follows:

$$392 \quad t_d = (k_d^* - 1) \Delta t + \frac{\alpha_{ij} (\lambda_{ij} - x_d)}{q_{ij}(k - k_d^*)}. \quad (7)$$

393 Consider now the single pipe of Fig. 5 in which a water parcel moves under the ef-
 394 fect of the uncertain water flow \tilde{q}_{ij} . Since we have an interval of possible flow values, the
 395 variable x_d will also be an interval. The interval of possible positions for the water par-
 396 cel $\tilde{x}_d \in [\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d]$ can be calculated as follows:

$$397 \quad [\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d] = \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_{ij}} \sum_{m=1}^{k_d} [q_{ij}(k - m), \bar{q}_{ij}(k - m)]. \quad (8)$$

398 Using interval arithmetic (Daumas et al., 2009), we can express (8) as:

$$399 \quad [\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d] = \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_{ij}} \left[\sum_{m=1}^{k_d} q_{ij}(k - m), \sum_{m=1}^{k_d} \bar{q}_{ij}(k - m) \right]. \quad (9)$$

400 The interval $[\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d]$ can reside in one of six positions, with respect to the pipe length,
 401 as illustrated in Fig. 5. The interval of possible positions $[\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d]$ is used to deduce the
 402 detention time and upstream nodes. Because this is an interval, there will be many possi-
 403 ble detention times that may correspond to different upstream nodes. In (9) we grad-
 404 ually increase delay k_d until: (i) both \underline{x}_d and \bar{x}_d are outside the pipe range, i.e., $[\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d] \not\subset$

Case 1:	$0 < [\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d] < \lambda_{ij}$
Case 2:	$0 < \underline{x}_d < \lambda_{ij}, \bar{x}_d > \lambda_{ij}$
Case 3:	$\underline{x}_d < 0, \bar{x}_d < \lambda_{ij}$
Case 4:	$\underline{x}_d < 0, \bar{x}_d > \lambda_{ij}$
Case 5:	$[\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d] > \lambda_{ij}$
Case 6:	$[\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d] < 0$

Figure 5. The interval $[\underline{x}_d, \bar{x}_d]$ with respect to the pipe length

Function 1 *Upstream&Time*

Input: node j , pipe l_{ij} , time-step k , flow bounds $\tilde{q}_{ij}(k, \dots, k - m)$

begin

- 1: $k_d \leftarrow 1$
- 2: **repeat**
- 3: Calculate $[x_d, \bar{x}_d]$ using (9)
- 4: **Case 1** : $k_d \leftarrow k_d + 1$
- 5: **Case 2 – 6** : Calculate delay t_d and node p
- 6: Add in \mathcal{T}_d and \mathcal{N}_p respectively
- 7: $k_d \leftarrow k_d + 1$
- 8: **until** $([x_d, \bar{x}_d] \not\subset [0, \lambda_{ij}]) \vee (k_d = k)$

return $\mathcal{T}_d, \mathcal{N}_p$

405 $[0, \lambda_{ij}]$ or (ii) the time boundary is reached, i.e., $k_d = k$. For each iteration that either
 406 x_d or \bar{x}_d are outside the pipe range, the detention time t_d is calculated using (7) and saved
 407 along with the corresponding upstream node. When evaluating (7), the lower bound of
 408 flows should be used if x_d is outside the pipe range, and the upper bound of flows should
 409 be used if \bar{x}_d is outside the pipe range. This procedure calculates two sets: \mathcal{T}_d contain-
 410 ing the possible time delays and \mathcal{N}_p containing the possible upstream nodes correspond-
 411 ing to each time delay. The two sets have a one-to-one element correspondence, denoted
 412 as $\mathcal{T}_d \rightarrow \mathcal{N}_p$.

413 **3.4 Function 2: *PipeContribution* — Chlorine and bulk reaction rate**
 414 **contribution of a pipe to a node**

415 The methodology for finding the interval of possible chlorine contributions $\tilde{c}_{ij}(k) =$
 416 $[\underline{c}_{ij}(k), \bar{c}_{ij}(k)]$, of a single pipe l_{ij} to a node j (as in Fig. 4) is described and implemented
 417 in Function *PipeContribution*. The function also finds the bounds on the possible bulk
 418 reaction rate contribution $\tilde{r}_{ij}^b(k) = [\underline{r}_{ij}^b(k), \bar{r}_{ij}^b(k)]$ of pipe l_{ij} to node j .

419 Uncertainty on chlorine decay rates is considered in this function for the calcula-
 420 tion of chlorine concentration: the uncertain wall reaction rate of the specific pipe given
 421 by $\tilde{r}_{ij}^w = [\underline{r}_{ij}^w, \bar{r}_{ij}^w]$ and the uncertain and time-varying bulk reaction rate of the upstream
 422 node given by $\tilde{r}_p^b(k) = [\underline{r}_p^b(k), \bar{r}_p^b(k)]$. The upstream node chlorine concentration is also
 423 uncertain given by the interval $\tilde{c}_p(k) = [\underline{c}_p(k), \bar{c}_p(k)]$. The interval of uncertain pipe wall
 424 reaction rates \tilde{r}_{ij}^w is assumed known, derived from knowledge of pipe material. The in-
 425 terval states $\tilde{r}_p^b(k)$ and $\tilde{c}_p(k)$ are calculated recursively by Function *BoundCheck*. Con-
 426 sidering the availability of sets \mathcal{T}_d and \mathcal{N}_p , given by Function *Upstream&Time*, the chlo-
 427 rine contribution bounds of pipe l_{ij} to node j is found as follows:

$$428 \quad \underline{c}_{ij}(k) = \begin{cases} \min_m & e^{(\tilde{r}_{ij}^w + \tilde{r}_i^b(k-m))\Delta t m} \cdot \tilde{c}_i(k - m) \\ \text{s.t.} & m \in \mathcal{T}_d \rightarrow i \in \mathcal{N}_p \end{cases}, \quad (10)$$

429 while $\bar{c}_{ij}(k)$ is found by solving (10) as a maximization problem. These problems are solved
 430 using interval arithmetic and enumeration of the possible time-steps $m \in \mathcal{T}_d$. Similarly,
 431 the bounds on possible bulk reaction rate contribution of pipe l_{ij} to node j is found by
 432 solving the following problem:

$$433 \quad \underline{r}_{ij}^b(k) = \begin{cases} \min_m & \tilde{r}_i^b(k - m) \\ \text{s.t.} & m \in \mathcal{T}_d \rightarrow i \in \mathcal{N}_p \end{cases}, \quad (11)$$

434 while $\bar{r}_{ij}^b(k)$ is found by solving (11) as a maximization problem.

Function 2 *PipeContribution***Input:** node j , pipe l_{ij} , time-step k **begin**

- 1: Get \mathcal{N}_p and \mathcal{T}_d by calling F1:*Upstream&Time*
- 2: **for** $m \in \mathcal{T}_d \rightarrow i \in \mathcal{N}_p$ **do**
- 3: Get $\tilde{c}_i(k-m)$ and $\tilde{r}_i^b(k-m)$ by calling F4:*BoundCheck*
- 4: **end for**
- 5: Solve (10) to get $\tilde{c}_{ij}(k)$
- 6: Solve (11) to get $\tilde{r}_{ij}^b(k)$

return $\tilde{c}_{ij}(k), \tilde{r}_{ij}^b(k)$

3.5 Function 3: *PipesJunction* — Chlorine concentration and bulk reaction rate at pipe junctions

This section describes the methodology for finding the chlorine concentration and bulk reaction rate bounds of a junction node that receives water from multiple pipes. The methodology is implemented in *PipesJunction*.

This function utilizes Assumption 2.2, which dictates that when multiple pipes bring water into a node the water and chlorine in the water mix instantly and completely. In the case when no uncertainty is considered, this is described by (2). In the case when uncertainties are present, all quantities in (2) will be represented by intervals. The interval of possible values for chlorine concentration at node j , indicated by $\tilde{c}_j(k) = [\underline{c}_j(k), \bar{c}_j(k)]$, is calculated by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\underline{c}_j(k) = \begin{cases} \min_{q_{ij}} & \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}_j(k)} q_{ij}(k) [\underline{c}_{ij}(k), \bar{c}_{ij}(k)]}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}_j(k)} q_{ij}(k)} \\ \text{s.t.} & \underline{q}_{ij}(k) < q_{ij}(k) < \bar{q}_{ij}(k) \end{cases}, \quad (12)$$

while $\bar{c}_j(k)$ is found by solving (12) as a maximization problem. The interval $[\underline{c}_{ij}(k), \bar{c}_{ij}(k)]$ is given by *PipeContribution*. Problem (12) is a linear fractional problem with interval coefficients which can be solved using the formulation described in (Borza et al., 2013).

The bulk reaction rate of the water arriving at a node of interest is calculated in a similar manner. Assumption 2.2 is used which implies that bulk reaction rate is proportional to the volume of water mixing from each water source. The interval of possible bulk reaction rates at node j , indicated by $\tilde{r}_j^b(k) = [r_j^b(k), \bar{r}_j^b(k)]$, is calculated as follows:

$$r_j^b(k) = \begin{cases} \min_{q_{ij}} & \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}_j(k)} q_{ij}(k) [r_{ij}^b(k), \bar{r}_{ij}^b(k)]}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}_j(k)} q_{ij}(k)} \\ \text{s.t.} & \underline{q}_{ij}(k) < q_{ij}(k) < \bar{q}_{ij}(k) \end{cases}, \quad (13)$$

while $\bar{r}_j^b(k)$ is found by solving (13) as a maximization problem.

3.6 Function 4: *BoundCheck* — Chlorine concentration and bulk reaction rate bounds at a node

Function *BoundCheck* is the top-level function of the proposed methodology, which is called to calculate the chlorine concentration bounds of a general node j . The function checks if the boundary conditions have been reached, i.e., if the initial time-step $k = 0$ has been reached (time boundary) or if the node of interest is an input node (space boundary). If any of the above is true then the chlorine concentration and bulk reaction rate of the node is known, otherwise, Function *PipesJunction* is called to calculate the chlorine concentration and bulk reaction rate bounds of node j .

Function 3 *PipesJunction*

Input: node j , time-step k , flow bounds $\tilde{q}(k)$ **begin**

- 1: Find $\mathcal{P}_j(k)$
- 2: **for** $i \in \mathcal{P}_j(k)$ **do**
- 3: Find $\tilde{c}_{ij}(k)$ and $\tilde{r}_{ij}^b(k)$ by calling F2:*PipeContribution*
- 4: **end for**
- 5: Solve (12) to get $\tilde{c}_j(k)$
- 6: Solve (13) to get $\tilde{r}_j^b(k)$

return $\tilde{c}_j(k), \tilde{r}_j^b(k)$

Function 4 *BoundCheck*

Input: node j , time-step k **begin**

- 1: **if** $k = 0$ **then**
- 2: **return** $\tilde{c}_j(0), \tilde{r}_j^b(0)$
- 3: **end if**
- 4: **if** $j \in \mathcal{U}$ **then**
- 5: **return** $\tilde{c}_j(k), \tilde{r}_j^b(k)$
- 6: **end if**
- 7: Find $\tilde{c}_j(k)$ and $\tilde{r}_j^b(k)$ by calling F3:*PipesJunction*

return $\tilde{c}_j(k), \tilde{r}_j^b(k)$

4 Real-time chlorine decay rate estimation in tanks

In this section, the methodology for estimating the chlorine decay rate inside a water tank which receives water from different sources is described. In many water transport networks, water from various sources is first stored in tanks and then distributed to the rest of the network. Water supplied from different sources may have varying quality characteristics; for example it may contain different concentrations of organic matter, which in turn affects chlorine decay rates. The quality characteristics of each source may be unknown and so would be the corresponding chlorine decay rate parameters.

In this work, we assume that hydraulic sensors are used to monitor the tank hydraulic states. Moreover, chlorine concentration sensors are installed at the input and output of the tanks. Under these conditions, a chlorine bulk reaction rate estimation scheme is designed to estimate in real-time the changing characteristic of water in tanks. The time-varying bulk reaction rate estimation algorithm is then used in conjunction with the BUBA to improve the chlorine concentration bounding estimates in the network.

4.1 Chlorine estimation in tanks

The model used in this work for calculating chlorine concentration in a tank which receives water from multiple water sources makes use of the following assumptions:

- There is instant and complete mixing of water and chlorine in the tank.
- Chlorine decay in tanks can be approximated by a linear, first order reaction model with time-varying decay rate.
- Water from each source is characterized by a distinct bulk reaction rate $r_i(k)$.
- The effect of tank wall reactions r^w is negligible compared to tank bulk reactions.

489 Considering the aforementioned assumptions, a chlorine concentration model for tanks
 490 is given by:

$$c_{out}(k+1) = \frac{v(k) - \Delta t q_{out}(k) + \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} (v_i(k) r_i(k))}{v(k+1)} c_{out}(k) + \frac{\Delta t \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} (q_{in,i}(k) c_{in,i}(k)) + u_c(k)}{v(k+1)}, \quad (14)$$

492 where:

- 493 • $c_{out}(k)$ is the chlorine concentration at the tank output at time-step k , which is
- 494 equal to the concentration inside the tank,
- 495 • $\mathbf{c}_{in}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s}$ is the vector of chlorine concentrations in the water of each of the
- 496 n_s different sources,
- 497 • $u_c(k) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the chlorine mass input inside the tank,
- 498 • $\mathbf{q}_{in}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s}$ is the vector of tank inflows from n_s different sources,
- 499 • $q_{out}(k) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the tank outflow,
- 500 • $v(k) = l_t(k) \alpha_t = \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} v_i(k)$ is the volume of water inside the tank,
- 501 • $l_t(k) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the tank water level,
- 502 • $\alpha_t \in \mathbb{R}$ is the tank base area,
- 503 • $v_i(k)$ is the volume of water in the tank from source i at time k and
- 504 • $r_i(k)$ is the unknown and time-varying chlorine decay rate of water from source
- 505 i .

506 The quantities in (14) that are needed to calculate c_{out} are either known or measured,
 507 except the vector of chlorine decay rates from each source, denoted in vector form as $\mathbf{r}(k) \in$
 508 $[r_1(k) r_2(k) \dots r_{n_s}(k)]$. The chlorine measurement vector \mathbf{y}_c (see Figure 2) is defined here
 509 as: $\mathbf{y}_c(k) = [\mathbf{c}_{in}^\top(k) c_{out}(k)]^\top$, and the hydraulic state measurement vector \mathbf{y}_h is de-
 510 fined as: $\mathbf{y}_h(k) = [\mathbf{q}_{in}^\top(k) q_{out}(k) l_t(k)]^\top$. In the following sections, the estimated pa-
 511 rameters are indicated with a hat, e.g., the estimated chlorine concentration at the tank
 512 output is given by \hat{c}_{out} .

513 4.2 Monitoring water volume from different sources

514 The hydraulic-states corresponding to tank water levels can be estimated using a
 515 discrete-time Luenberger observer, as shown in (Vrachimis et al., 2018). Water volumes
 516 inside the tank can be calculated using these water levels and the structure of the tank.
 517 Here, an extension of the discrete-time observer described in (Vrachimis et al., 2018) is
 518 proposed, able to estimate the water volume from each source inside a tank. First, an
 519 estimate of the total tank volume $\hat{v}(k)$ is calculated using the following observer struc-
 520 ture:

$$521 \hat{v}(k+1) = \hat{v}(k) + \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} q_{in,i}(k) - \Delta t q_{out}(k) + L_d (l_t(k) \alpha - \hat{v}(k)), \quad (15)$$

522 where $L_d \in (0, 1)$ is the discrete-time observer gain. To estimate the volume from each
 523 source i in the tank, the input $q_{in,i}$ and output $q_{out,i}$ from each source is needed. The
 524 input from each source is typically measured, however the output cannot be measured
 525 after the water is mixed in the tank. Using the assumption of complete mixing of wa-
 526 ter in the tank, it can also be assumed that the volume of water from each source ex-
 527 iting the tank at each time instant is proportional to the water volume from this source
 528 inside the tank, such that:

$$529 q_{out,i}(k) = v_i(k)/v(k) \cdot q_{out}(k). \quad (16)$$

530 Given (16), the water volume $\hat{v}_i(k)$ from each source i is estimated using $\hat{v}(k)$ as follows:

$$531 \begin{aligned} \hat{v}_i(k+1) &= \hat{v}_i(k) + \Delta t q_{in,i}(k) - \Delta t q_{out,i}(k) \\ &= \hat{v}_i(k) + \Delta t q_{in,i}(k) - \Delta t \frac{\hat{v}_i(k)}{\hat{v}(k)} q_{out}(k). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

532 Note that when calculating (17), mass conservation must be taken into account, by en-
533 suring that the total water volume in the tank is equal to the sum of individual water
534 volumes originating from each source, as follows:

$$535 \hat{v}(k+1) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} \hat{v}_i(k+1). \quad (18)$$

536 4.3 Initial decay rate estimates

537 The actual decay rates $\mathbf{r}(k)$ in (14) are unknown, however initial estimates $\hat{\mathbf{r}}(0)$
538 can be derived using historical data as a training set. The initial estimates may improve
539 the performance of the parameter estimation algorithm if they are close to the actual
540 parameter values. In this work, the initial estimates are mainly used to compare the per-
541 formance of chlorine estimation when using constant and time-varying decay rates. The
542 constant initial estimates are calculated using k_T chlorine measurements $c_{out}(k)$, $k \in$
543 $\{-k_T, \dots, -1\}$ at the tank output as a training set. The chlorine estimation function
544 of (14) is modified to consider constant decay rates \mathbf{r} and, in order to use already mea-
545 sured quantities, time delay is added, as follows:

$$546 \begin{aligned} \hat{c}_{out}(k, \mathbf{r}) &= \\ & \frac{\hat{v}(k-1) - \Delta t q_{out}(k-1) + \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} \hat{v}_i(k-1) r_i}{\hat{v}(k)} \hat{c}_{out}(k-1) \\ & + \frac{\Delta t \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} q_{in,i}(k-1) c_{in,i}(k-1) + u_c(k-1)}{\hat{v}(k)}, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

547 where $\hat{c}_{out}(k, \mathbf{r})$ is the estimation of chlorine concentration at time k using the constant
548 decay parameters \mathbf{r} . The initial estimates $\mathbf{r}(0)$ are calculated by solving the following
549 least squares optimization problem:

$$550 \hat{\mathbf{r}}(0) = \begin{cases} \arg \min_{\mathbf{r}} & \sum_{k=-k_T}^{-1} [c_{out}(k) - \hat{c}_{out}(k, \mathbf{r})]^2, \\ s.t. & \underline{\mathbf{r}} \leq \mathbf{r} \leq \bar{\mathbf{r}} \end{cases}, \quad (20)$$

551 where $\underline{\mathbf{r}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}}$ are vectors of known, conservative, lower and upper bounds on the de-
552 cay rates respectively.

553 4.4 Real-time parameter estimation scheme

554 Having the chlorine dynamics model with known parameters of (14) and an ini-
555 tial estimate of chlorine decay rates $\hat{\mathbf{r}}(0)$, a real-time parameter estimation scheme for
556 each source's decay rate can be designed. The chlorine concentration prediction model
557 of (14) is re-written by adding time-delay in order to use already known (measured) quan-
558 tities in the parameter estimation algorithm. The measured (known) terms $z(k)$, $\psi(k)$
559 and the unknown terms $\mathbf{r}(k)$ are then separated. To do this, we first define the known
560 terms $z(k)$ as follows:

$$561 \begin{aligned} z(k) &\triangleq \hat{v}(k) \cdot c_{out}(k) - \hat{v}(k-1) \cdot c_{out}(k-1) \\ & - \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} q_{in,i}(k-1) c_{in,i}(k-1) + \Delta t \cdot q_{out}(k-1) \cdot c_{out}(k-1) - u_c(k-1). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

562 The time-delayed version of the chlorine concentration model (14) is then re-written using
 563 $z(k)$ as follows:

$$564 \quad z(k) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} r_1(k-1) \\ \vdots \\ r_{n_s}(k-1) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{r}(k-1)}^\top \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} v_1(k-1) \\ \vdots \\ v_{n_s}(k-1) \end{bmatrix}}_{\boldsymbol{\psi}(k-1)} \Delta t c_{out}(k-1) \quad (22)$$

565 The actual decay rate parameters $\mathbf{r}(k)$ can be expressed using $z(k)$ and $\boldsymbol{\psi}(k-1)$ as follows:
 566

$$567 \quad z(k) = \mathbf{r}^\top(k-1)\boldsymbol{\psi}(k-1), \quad (23)$$

568 while the estimated parameters, denoted by $\hat{\mathbf{r}}(k)$, are given by:

$$569 \quad \hat{z}(k) \triangleq \hat{\mathbf{r}}^\top(k-1)\boldsymbol{\psi}(k-1) \quad (24)$$

570 The error between the measured and estimated quantities is then calculated as follows:

$$571 \quad \varepsilon(k) = \frac{z(k) - \hat{z}(k)}{m^2(k-1)} \quad (25)$$

572 where $m(k-1) > 0$ a normalized signal which bounds $\boldsymbol{\psi}(k-1)$ from above, e.g., $m^2(k-1) = 1 + \boldsymbol{\psi}^\top(k-1)\boldsymbol{\psi}(k-1)$. By performing Lyapunov analysis we get the algorithm
 573 to calculate the estimate $\hat{\mathbf{r}}(k)$ (Ioannou & Fidan, 2006):
 574

$$575 \quad \begin{aligned} \varepsilon(k) &= \frac{z(k) - \hat{\mathbf{r}}^\top(k-1)\boldsymbol{\psi}(k-1)}{m^2(k-1)} \\ \hat{\mathbf{r}}(k) &= \hat{\mathbf{r}}(k-1) + \Gamma\varepsilon(k)\boldsymbol{\psi}(k-1) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

576 where $\Gamma \in (0, 2)$ is a design parameter which affects how fast the parameter estimates
 577 change. As a practical note, the estimated decay rates from different sources are not expected
 578 to vary significantly in the course of a day, thus parameter Γ should be chosen
 579 to be relatively small.

580 Finally, an estimate of the overall chlorine decay rate at tank outflow $\hat{r}_{out}(k)$ is calculated
 581 by utilizing (16), which allows us to determine the contribution of each source
 582 to the current outflow:

$$583 \quad \hat{r}_{out}(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} \frac{\hat{v}_i(k)}{\hat{v}(k)} \cdot \hat{r}_i(k) \quad (27)$$

584 5 Case studies

585 5.1 Application on a transport network

586 In this case study, the ‘‘Hanoi’’ benchmark network (Fujiwara & Khang, 1990), an
 587 example of a water transport network shown in Fig. 6, is used to demonstrate the chlorine
 588 concentration bounds generated by the BUBA. Realistic water demands were generated
 589 based on real observations of consumption at the level of a District Metered Area
 590 (DMA), and assigned at the network nodes. The system is simulated for a period of 24
 591 hours, during which the demand at each node varies based on a unique pattern. The demands
 592 change every 5 minutes, which is equal to the discrete hydraulic-step used for this
 593 system. It is noted here that, computationally, the accuracy of the proposed methodology
 594 depends only on the water-quality time-step and the only requirement regarding the
 595 hydraulic time-step is to be equal or larger than the water-quality step. The hydraulic-
 596 step is typically defined by the frequency of measurements from hydraulic sensors, which
 597 are in turn used in a hydraulic-state estimation algorithm to provide new estimates. In
 598 practice, water-quality estimates are more accurate when hydraulic-state estimates of

599 higher resolution are used, considering the dependence of water-quality on the hydraulic
 600 dynamics. In the case when the hydraulic-step is larger than the water-quality step, the
 601 proposed algorithm replicates the most recently updated hydraulic states to use in the
 602 water-quality simulation.

603 Hydraulic model uncertainty is considered in the form of uncertain node demands
 604 and hydraulic model parameters. The uncertainty is considered to be bounded by a known
 605 bound. Specifically, for node demands the uncertainty upper bound is $\pm 10\%$ of the given
 606 value at each time-step. Uncertainty in the hydraulic model is considered in the form
 607 of uncertain pipe roughness coefficients, with an upper bound of $\pm 10\%$ of the given value
 608 for each pipe.

609 Chlorine concentration, is regulated at reservoir node 1. A set-point chlorine booster
 610 regulates the concentration at that point to 0.4 (mg/L). It is assumed that the initial
 611 concentration throughout the network is uniform and equal to 0.4 (mg/L). In this case
 612 study, for the purpose of comparing the BUBA with the EPANET simulator which does
 613 not support time-varying bulk reaction rates, the chlorine bulk reaction rate in the net-
 614 work is assumed constant, and it is set to $r_i^b = -0.5$ (1/day). Wall reactions are set to
 615 $r_{ij}^w = -0.25$ (m/day) for all pipes l_{ij} . These are typical values from investigations on
 616 real systems when a first-order chlorine decay model is considered, with the study in (Vasconcelos
 617 et al., 1997) reporting bulk reaction rates in the distribution system in the range of -0.08
 618 (1/day) to -1.32 (1/day) and wall reaction rates from 0 (m/day) to 1.52 (m/day). Rel-
 619 ative diffusivity effects are ignored. Water quality is solved with a time-step of $\Delta t =$
 620 1 minute.

621 Water quality model uncertainty is considered in the form of uncertain bulk reac-
 622 tion rate r^b and uncertain wall reaction rate r^w . The uncertainty on these parameters
 623 is assumed bounded, with an upper bound of $\pm 10\%$ of their given value.

624 Water-quality sensors in these systems are typically placed optimally, with respect
 625 to minimizing the impact of a potential contamination. Tools for sensor placement ex-
 626 ist in the literature, an example of which is the *S-Place* toolkit (Eliades et al., 2014). The
 627 *S-Place* toolkit places the sensors by minimizing the impact of all possible contamina-
 628 tions, considering also modeling uncertainty. *Impact* in *S-Place* is defined as the volume
 629 of contaminated water consumed in m^3 until the contamination is detected. For the Hanoi
 630 network, three sensors were optimally placed using *S-Place* at nodes $\mathcal{N}_s = \{5, 10, 24\}$.

631 Chlorine concentration bounds were generated by the BUBA given the aforemen-
 632 tioned case study parameters. To examine the validity of the bounds computed by the
 633 proposed BUBA, they are compared to bounds provided by extensive Monte-Carlo simu-
 634 lations (MCS) on the case study network, using the EPANET software (Rossman, 2000)
 635 in MATLAB with the help of the EPANET-MATLAB toolkit (Eliades et al., 2016). In
 636 total 30000 simulations were performed for the Hanoi network, where the uncertain pa-
 637 rameters were randomly varied inside their uncertainty bounds. In each simulation the
 638 minimum and maximum values of each quality state were saved. Quality tolerance in
 639 EPANET was set to 10^{-4} , to improve the accuracy of the calculated water quality state.
 640 Pumps and valves are represented by zero-length elements in both the EPANET and BUBA
 641 simulators. The generated bounds on the locations of the three sensors are illustrated
 642 in Fig. 7. It is shown that BUBA provides tight bounds, close to those generated by the
 643 computationally intensive MCS.

644 5.2 Application on a District Metered Area network

645 In this case study, the “CY-DMA” network, shown in Fig. 8 is used to demonstrate
 646 the chlorine concentration bounds generated by the BUBA. “CY-DMA” is an example
 647 of a District Metered Area (DMA) network, as it was created based on a real DMA net-
 648 work in Cyprus (Vrachimis et al., 2020). Realistic water demands were generated based

Figure 6. The “Hanoi” benchmark transport network and location of chlorine sensors.

Figure 7. Chlorine concentration bounds generated by the proposed BUBA and 30000 Monte-Carlo simulations at three sensor locations on the “Hanoi” benchmark transport network.

649 on real observations of consumption at the level of a DMA, and assigned at the network
 650 nodes. For the “CY-DMA” network, nine sensors were optimally placed using *S-Place*
 651 toolkit at nodes $\mathcal{N}_s = \{3, 17, 28, 41, 44, 55, 65, 82, 90\}$. The rest of the case study pa-
 652 rameters are the same as in the “Hanoi” network case study.

653 Chlorine concentration bounds were generated by the BUBA given the aforemen-
 654 tioned case study parameters and compared to bounds generated by 30000 Monte-Carlo
 655 simulations. The results on the locations of the nine sensors are illustrated in Fig. 9. It
 656 is shown that the BUBA provides tight bounds on some states (nodes 3, 17, 44), how-
 657 ever in some states it provides wider bounds, such as at node 55 where the BUBA bound
 658 width is approximately five time larger than the MCS bound width. This is mainly due
 659 to the uncertainty in water flows, which can significantly affect chlorine concentration
 660 especially in the case when flow reversals occur. The BUBA bounds are generated con-
 661 sidering all the possible cases explained by the system uncertainty, whereas it would take
 662 a huge number of MCS to generate the extreme cases calculated by the BUBA. This il-

Figure 8. The “CY-DMA” district metered area network and location of chlorine sensors.

Figure 9. Chlorine concentration bounds generated by the proposed BUBA and 30000 Monte-Carlo simulations at nine sensor locations on the “CY-DMA” district metered area network.

663 illustrates the benefit of the proposed algorithm to *capture bounds that would be difficult*
 664 *to capture even with extensive simulations.*

Figure 10. Diagram of the real transport network used in this case study

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5.3 Case study on a real transport network

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The proposed methodology is demonstrated using real data from a water transport network in a large city in Cyprus, shown in Fig. 10. This network has complete hydraulic state observability, achieved by flow measurements at the inflows and outflows of the network and a level sensor at the tank. It also contains three chlorine concentration sensors, one at the supply tank inflow, one at the tank outflow and one at a network branch.

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The tank volume observer described in Section 4.2, uses the tank level measurements as well as the flow measurements $q_{0a}(k)$, $q_{0b}(k)$ and $q_1(k)$ to estimate the total water volume inside the tank $\hat{v}(k)$ at each time-step, as well as the individual water volume from each of the two water sources, indicated by $\hat{v}_a(k)$ and $\hat{v}_b(k)$. The estimation of the two separate water volumes in the tank is shown in Fig. 11(c).

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Chlorine sensors are installed at the inflow and outflow of the tank, with their measurements indicated by c_0 and c_1 respectively (Fig. 10). These measurements can be used to estimate the chlorine bulk reaction rate of water from each source, using the estimated water volumes, the chlorine measurements $c_0(k)$, $c_1(k)$ and the chlorine injection at the tank $u_c(k)$. First, an initial estimate of the reaction rates of each source is calculated using historical data. The optimization of (20) is solved, with conservative bounds on the decay rates set to $\bar{\mathbf{r}} = [0, 0]$ and $\underline{\mathbf{r}} = [-1, -1]$. The calculated reaction rates for each source are: $[\hat{r}_a(0), \hat{r}_b(0)] = [-0.0100, -0.0256]$ (1/hour). The chlorine concentration inside the tank can be estimated using these constant reaction rates; we will indicate the estimated chlorine concentration for this case by $\hat{c}_1^0(k)$. However, as seen from Fig. 11(a), there is significant discrepancy between the estimated $\hat{c}_1^0(k)$ and measured $c_1(k)$ concentration when using a constant reaction rate due to the varying water-quality characteristics in the tank.

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The chlorine bulk reaction rate $r_{out}(k)$ at the tank output (and inside the tank) can be estimated in real-time using the parameter estimation algorithm described in Section 4. The parameter estimation algorithm estimates the reaction rate $\hat{r}_a(k)$ of source a and the reaction rate $\hat{r}_b(k)$ of source b , as seen in Fig. 11(b). These two reaction-rate estimates are then used with the water volume estimates $\hat{v}_a(k)$ and $\hat{v}_b(k)$ to calculate the total reaction rate $r_{out}(k)$ as described in (27). The estimated chlorine concentration in the tank $\hat{c}_1(k)$ using this time-varying reaction rate, is a better approximation of the measured concentration $c_1(k)$ than when a constant reaction rate is used, as illustrated in Fig. 11(a).

Figure 11. (a): Measurement of chlorine concentration at the tank output $c_1(k)$ compared to its estimation when using a constant bulk reaction rate $\hat{c}_1^0(k)$, and when using a time-varying bulk reaction rate $\hat{c}_1(k)$. (b): Estimation of chlorine reaction rates of source a and source b , and the estimated total reaction rate in the tank $\hat{r}(k)$. (c): Estimation of water volume from source a and source b in the tank.

698 The proposed Backtracking Uncertainty Bounding Algorithm described in Section
 699 3 is now used to calculate chlorine concentration bounds at the measured location c_2 inside the network,
 700 using the estimated time-varying tank bulk reaction rate $\hat{r}_{out}(k)$. The Iterative Hydraulic Interval State Estimator (IHISE) proposed in (Vrachimis et al., 2019)
 701 is first used to calculate a bounded estimate of water flows in the network $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}(k) = [\underline{\mathbf{q}}(k), \bar{\mathbf{q}}(k)]$
 702 using the available flow and head measurements. The IHISE considers 20% uncertainty
 703 on flow and tank level measurements. The BUBA uses the uncertain flows $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}(k)$, while
 704 it also considers 30% uncertainty on the given pipe wall reaction rates \mathbf{r}^w . The bulk reaction
 705 rate r^b of each water parcel tracked by the BUBA, is equal to the tank bulk reaction
 706 rate which is given by the parameter estimation algorithm. For example, if a water
 707 parcel i is exiting the tank at time-step k then the bulk reaction rate of the parcel
 708 is $r_i^b = \hat{r}_{out}(k)$. Moreover, 30% uncertainty is considered on the bulk reaction rate r_i^b
 709 of each water parcel.
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711 The chlorine concentration bounds $\tilde{c}_2(k)$ calculated by the BUBA are compared
 712 in Fig. 12 to the measured concentration $c_2(k)$ in the network. In the same figure, the
 713 benefit of estimating in real-time the reaction rate in the supply tank is examined by comparing the BUBA bounds when using a constant reaction rate in the tank (Fig. 12(a)),
 714 with the BUBA bounds when using the estimated time-varying reaction rate (Fig. 12(a)).
 715 The results show a slight improvement on the bounding estimates when using the estimated
 716 time-varying decay rate, as they better enclose the measurements, which are assumed to be fault-free during the examined period. Note that for the specific case study,
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Figure 12. Measured chlorine concentration $c_2(k)$ compared to the BUBA calculated chlorine concentration bounds when (a) using a constant bulk reaction rate and (b) when using a time-varying bulk reaction rate which is estimated in real-time.

719 the bounds generated by the BUBA are equal to zero for the first 2 hours and 45 min-
 720 utes. This is due to the travel time of chlorine from the tank to the measured branch
 721 of the network. Before this time, the BUBA gives zero bounds because of the assump-
 722 tion that the initial chlorine concentration in the network was zero.

723 6 Conclusions and future work

724 This work presents a comprehensive methodology for generating bounded chlorine
 725 concentration estimates at sensor locations in WDN, suitable to be used for sensor fault
 726 and contamination detection purposes. The proposed Backtracking Uncertainty Bound-
 727 ing Algorithm (BUBA) is able to calculate tight chlorine concentration bounds, given
 728 bounded hydraulic-state estimates and bounds on water quality parameters. The bounds
 729 are validated and compared to a large number of Monte-Carlo simulations on two bench-
 730 mark networks. Additionally, the BUBA is designed to facilitate time-varying bulk re-
 731 action rates, which occur in systems with multiple water sources. This is demon-
 732 strated by designing a real-time bulk reaction rate estimation algorithm in tanks with water ori-
 733 ginating from different sources. The parameter estimation algorithm and the proposed
 734 BUBA are then applied on a real network case study with real data. An improvement
 735 is shown in the estimated chlorine concentration bounds when using the real-time bulk
 736 reaction rate estimates.

737 The proposed methodology for bounded chlorine concentration estimation has some
 738 drawbacks such as it may need some time to produce accurate results when the initial
 739 concentration assumed in the network is not accurate. This effect may be amplified in
 740 large networks with slow water velocities. Moreover, it uses a linear, first order model
 741 for chlorine decay dynamics. In future work, the formulation of this methodology when
 742 using a more complex model of chlorine decay will be demonstrated. Moreover, only a
 743 real-time parameter estimation algorithm for the decay rates in tanks is demonstrated,
 744 however, the proposed methodology is able to use the path information provided by the
 745 BUBA to also facilitate a wall reaction coefficient estimation algorithm, which will fur-

746 ther reduce parameter uncertainty. The quantification of the parameter estimation un-
 747 certainty in order to properly define parameter uncertainty bounds during the param-
 748 eter estimation process should also be investigated.

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755 Nomenclature

c_i	chlorine concentration at node i
c_{ij}	chlorine contribution of pipe l_{ij} to node j
$f_c(\cdot)$	nonlinear function for calculating chlorine concentration
\mathcal{G}	directed graph of water network
h_i	head state at node i
k_d	elapsed time-steps of water parcel in pipe
\mathcal{L}	set of all links
$l_t(k)$	tank water level
\mathcal{M}	general model of water network
m	memory of functions $f_c(\cdot)$ and $\tilde{f}_c(\cdot)$
\mathcal{N}	set of all nodes
\mathcal{N}_p	set containing possible upstream nodes
\mathcal{N}_s	set of sensor nodes in the network
n_l	number of links
n_n	number of nodes
n_s	number of different water sources from which a tank receives water
$\mathcal{P}_j(k)$	set of all pipes that bring water into node j at time k
q_{ij}	water flow state in link connecting node i to node j
756 r^b	bulk reaction rate of chlorine in the network
r_{ij}^w	wall reaction rate of chlorine in pipe l_{ij}
\mathcal{T}_d	set containing possible time delays
t_d	detention time of water parcel in pipe
\mathcal{U}	set of nodes with known chlorine concentration
u_i	chlorine mass injection at node i
$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$	interval vector notation: $\underline{\mathbf{v}}$ the lower bound and $\bar{\mathbf{v}}$ the upper bound vector
$v(k)$	tank water volume at time-step k
x_d	auxiliary quantity defining the position of a water parcel in a pipe
\mathbf{x}_h	complete hydraulic-state of the network
y_c	chlorine concentration measurements
y_h	hydraulic sensor measurements
α_{ij}	cross section area of pipe l_{ij}
α_t	tank cross section area
$\boldsymbol{\theta}$	vector of network parameters
$\boldsymbol{\theta}_h$	vector of hydraulic-model parameters
$\boldsymbol{\theta}_r$	vector of quality-model parameters
λ_{ij}	length of pipe l_{ij}

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